

Optical Counterfeit Protection with Smartphones

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ABSTRACT

We propose a novel characterization of surfaces implemented using the macro-enabled cameras of modern smartphones and artificial intelligence algorithms. Each object is characterized and identified by a unique fingerprint of the surface's optical characteristics of the object. The technology is primarily designed for paper but suitable for all non-reflective surfaces such as cardboard, plastic and numerous metals. For the description of the surface characteristics, key points are first determined using local feature descriptors like SIFT, ORB or feature descriptors from neural networks. For each key point, feature vectors that are as invariant as possible are then determined, which together describe the fingerprint of the surface. A supervised classification approach is used to identify the individual fingerprint from a database. This approach was evaluated in practice using a label-printing machine and an industrial camera with similar optical properties of macro cameras of current high-quality smartphones. It could be shown that a single label can be identified from a set of 100,000 identical printed labels using the presented approach.

KEYWORDS: Optical surface characteristics, local feature descriptors, SIFT, neural networks, keypoints, feature vectors.

INTRODUCTION

Static security features have been used so far in retail to identify high-value objects. The classic hologram, for example, is based on the concept of very small diffractive but static structures that are used to prevent reproduction by classic copiers.

The research areas of pattern recognition and image classification have improved a lot recently which gave rise to powerful algorithms that can identify a single image from a dataset in order of millions. Most of the research is based on extracting keypoints and descriptors from the image and use them to represent the image mathematically. Our idea is to use the same approach and apply the technology to address the counterfeiting problems. We present a novel approach that uses the irregularities in printing process and generates an unique finger print to represent the original printed label which can be verified.

CONCEPT

Given a query image the goal is to evaluate if the image is captured from a legitimate source or is it faked by any means. Our approach is to use keypoint matching technique and combine it with an efficient similarity search process to achieve this goal. The technology is currently reliable on the current day smartphones that has this macro capability and certain industrial cameras that have really good resolution.

Extraction of keypoints can be done using the popular local feature extractors like SIFT[4],SURF, ORB or according to Deep Graphical Feature Learning for the Feature Matching Problem[1], D2-NET[2], LF-NET [3] modern day neural network architectures are more robust and can extract the keypoints more efficiently. Either way after extracting the keypoints a database is built by selecting the first “n” number of keypoints sorted based on the response. This yields a matrix of dimensions [nx64] for each image, every vector in this matrix corresponds to a single keypoint descriptor. Hence considering there are “m” images the dataset can be of the size [mx[nx64]].

Assuming a dataset is constructed and stored in either a cloud-based platform or over a storage unit which is accessible on a local network that has a collection of original feature points, say $F = [f_1, f_2, f_3, \dots, f_n]$ where $f_n = [1 \times 64]$ assuming n as the sorted keypoints and f_n represents a keypoint descriptor corresponding to one image. The next set of feature points corresponding to the query vector (which were the keypoints extracted in the same format that was used to build the database) represented as $G = [g_1, g_2, g_3, \dots, g_n]$ where $g_n = [1 \times 64]$. The aim is to find out the vectors that maximizes a similarity function `S` in the following way,

$$\max S \left([f_i]_{i=1}^n, [g_j]_{j=1}^n \right) \text{ ---- (1)}$$

Where S is the nearest neighbor search function and n is the number of keypoints in sorted order. If a particular vector is having maximum similarity and also passes the Lowe`s ratio test[4], the threshold was set to 0.75, then we count that particular keypoint is a positive match. Now when we use a database of images

which have about m images then the image with maximum positive matches is termed as the match to query vector. We also internally include a threshold to classify between the fake and original.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The tools that were used for conducting the experiments were an industrial camera which can capture images about 10 to 20 images per second and the iPhone 13 Pro. For robustness we currently are employing SIFT for extracting the keypoints and there by performing an optimized nearest neighbor search.

Each evaluation is conducted in a total of 3 stages. The initial stage corresponds to acquiring the data and building of database, the second stage is to evaluate the search using the images captured by the same sensor that was used to capture the images which are stored in the database. The third stage is to use a smartphone to acquire the query image and to perform the search. The pipeline for building the data base and searching the query is as follows:

- Initial step involves capturing images using the industrial camera over a production line that has the capacity to capture about 100,000 images automatically.
- Next the images that are stored locally were transferred to a cloud-based storage service to extract the feature points that represent the images.
- The images were now discarded and the keypoints were stored in a database that uses the key value, a sequential number to retrieve the feature matrix corresponding to the image that was saved.
- Once the service is active the user can either use an industrial camera or smart phone to connect and transfer the stream of images captured to the web service which has the backend connectivity to the database where the image representations are stored. The communication is made by building a secure channel using an RPC request type communication protocol.
- After receiving each image, the search algorithm is triggered and computes the score in accordance with the equation (1) and Lowe score mentioned in Concept section above.
- Finally, the same score is communicated back to the smart phone using the response protocol for that particular RPC request.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experiments that were conducted as described in Materials and Methods section comprises of 100,000 images which were used to extract keypoints and build the database. The search process is designed in such a way that all the 100,000 images were again captured at a different time stamp by a different industrial camera which has the same settings. The second set of images were reported to be the search queries. After the experiment all the search images found out their original counterparts successfully and there were no False positives reported. The round-trip time for sending the image as request and getting the response time back is about 700 to 1200 milli seconds on an average depending on the network strength. The second set of experiments is based on the smartphone client. The large-scale tests are still in experimental phase but in cross platform experiments the images captured from the iphone have also found the original counter parts without any false matches.

CONCLUSIONS

The technology proposed has the potential to identify the image based on the minute irregularities that appear on the print surface which are unique and can correspond only to that particular print label. Adapting the recent state-of-the art neural networks will even improve the performance and gives more robustness towards the cross-platform searches.

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